

PAYVANDLASH ISHLARI TEXNOLOGIYASI MASALASI

Xamroliyev Abduhalim Umaraliyevich,
Farg‘ona viloyati Oltiariq tumani, 2 son kasb hunar
maktabi payvandlash asoslari fani o‘qituvchisi

Annotasiya: Maqolada payvandlash tushunchasi, payvandlash xududini sovutish tezligi, payvandlash birikmasi, metal choki, uning mexanik xossalari va boshqalar haqida qisqacha mulohazalar keltiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Payvandlash, metal, chegara, qotishma, metal plastika, birikma.

Аннотация: В статье даются краткие комментарии о понятии сварки, скорости охлаждения зоны сварки, сварном соединении, металле сварного шва, его механических свойствах и др.

Ключевые слова: Сварка, металл, граница, сплав, пластичность металла, соединение.

Abstract: The article provides brief comments on the concept of welding, the cooling rate of the welding zone, the welding joint, the metal seam, its mechanical properties, etc.

Keywords: Welding, metal, boundary, alloy, metal plastic, joint.

Payvandlash – metallar, qotishmalar va turli materiallarni plastik deformatsiyalash yoki birikilayotgan qismlar orasini qizdirish bilan atomlararo birikish natijasida ajralmas birikma hosil qiluvchi texnologik jarayondir. Atomlararo kuchlar ta'siri natijasida birikmalar hosil qilish jarayoniga materiallarni payvandlash deyiladi. Ma'lum bo'lishicha detal metalining yuzadagi

atomlari, erkin, to'yinmagan aloqalari mavjud, bular atomlararo kuch ta'siri masofasida bo'lgan har xil atom va molekullarni o'z ichiga oladi. Agar ikki metall detalni atomlararo kuch ta'siri masofasigacha yaqinlashtirsak, ya'ni metall ichida qanday masofada bo'lishsa shungacha, unda tutashgan yuzalarning bir butun ulanishini ko'ramiz. Birikish jarayoni energiya xarjisiz va tez o'z ixtiyoriy amaliy oniy kechadi.

Ayrim metallar xona haroratida nafaqat oddiy tutashishda, balki kuchli qisishda ham birikmaydi. Qattiq metallarni birikishiga uning qattiqligi xalaqit beradi, tutashish qismiga qanchalik ishlov berilmasin, ularni tutashtirishda ko'p joylari tutashmaydi. Birikish jarayoniga metall yuzalarining kirligi yomon ta'sir etadi. Bularga – oksidlar, yog'li plyonkalar va boshqalar hamda gaz molekullarining adsorblashgan qatlamlari kiradi, va metall yuzasi uzoq vaqt toza saqlanishi uning yuqori vakuumda ushlab turishiga bog'liq.

2.3. Texnologik imkoniyatlar Chok metali qotishi bilan undagi struktura o'zgarishlari tugamaydi. Masalan, po'latni payvandlashda birlamchi kristallitlar ular hosil bo'lgan zahotiyuq yuqori haroratlarda ($750...1500^{\circ}\text{C}$) mavjud bo'ladigan austenitdan – uglerod bilan legirlovchi elementlarning γ - temirdagi qattiq eritmasidan iborat bo'ladi. Sovitish jarayonida austenit parchalanib, po'latning tarkibi va sovitish tezligiga qarab boshqa fazalarga: plastiklik ferritga, ancha mustahkam perlitga mustahkam, biroq, plastikligi kam martensitga aylanadi. Payvandlash hududini sovitish tezligi, odatda, katta va struktura o'zgarishlari oxirigacha yuz berishga ulgurmaydi. Binobarin, payvand birikmani sovitish tezligini o'zgartirib, uni qizdirib yoki sun'iy sovitib, ba'zi chegaralarda chok metallining ikkilamchi kristallanishini va uning mexanik xossalarini ba'zi chegaralarda boshqarishi mumkin. Qizdirish manbai ajratib chiqaradigan issiqlik yordamida payvandlashda, issiqlik asosiy metallga tarqaladi. Uning hududlari payvandlash vannasi chegarasida erish haroratigacha qiziydi va vannadan uzoqroq hududda esa atrof-muhit haroratida bo'ladi. Bu hol metall strukturasi ta'sir

etmay qolmaydi. Metallni qizdirish va sovitish natijasida asosiy metall strukturasi va xossalari o'zgarishi yuz beradigan hududini termik ta'sir zonasi (TTZ) deb ataladi. Ayni nuqta haroratining vaqt mobaynida o'zgarishi termik sikl deyiladi. TTZ ning har qaysi nuqtasi payvandlashda o'zining termik sikliga ega bo'ladi. Demak, TTZ dagi metall payvandlash natijasida bir necha tur termik ishlovlarga duchor bo'ladi. Shuning uchun TTZ da strukturasi va xossalari turlicha aniq ajralib turadigan hududlar borligi kuzatiladi.

Chok metaliga bevosita to'liq erimagan hududi tutashib turadi. Bu – chok metallidan bevosita asosiy metallga o'tadigan yupqa (bir necha mikronga teng) polosacha bo'lib, asosiy metallning qisman erigan donalaridan iborat bo'ladi. To'liq erimagan hudud metali kimyoviy jihatdan bir xil emas, unda kuchlanishlar ta'sir qiladi. Undan keyin qizib ketish hududi keladi. Bu hududda metall 1130°C dan yuqori haroratlarga qiziydi, donlar kuchli o'sib ulguradi va sovitilganida maydalanmaydi. Bu yerda donlarning chegaralari bo'yicha emas, balki ularning ichida ignalar yoki plastinkalar ko'rinishdagi plastik faza – ferrit ajralib chiqishi mumkin. Bunday struktura vidmanshted struktura deb ataladi. Uning mexanik xossalari yomon, xususan zarbiy qovushqoqligi past. To'liq erimagan va qizib ketish hududlari birgalikda chok atrofi zonasi deb ataladi. 900–1100°C da me'yorlash (to'la qayta kristallanish) hududi hosil bo'ladi, uning strukturasi mayda donli bo'ladi. Bu hududda metallning yuqori haroratda turishi davomiyligi uncha ko'p emas, don o'sib ulgurmaydi, sovitilganda esa maydalanadi. Shuning uchun, metall bu yerda: eng yuqori mexanik xossalarga ega bo'ladi. Chala kristallizatsiyalash hududi haroratlar diapazoni 723–900°C bilan belgilanadi. Bu hududda oxirgi struktura qayta kristallanishga ulgurmagan yirik donlardan va ular orasida joylashgan qayta kristallanishda hosil bo'lgan mayda donlardan iborat bo'ladi. Metall bu yerda: mexanik xossalari bo'yicha me'yorlash hududidagiga nisbatan yomon, biroq qizib ketish hududidagiga nisbatan yaxshiroq. Rekristalizatsiya hududida metall 500–723°C haroratgacha qiziydi. Metallning

strukturasi o'zgaraydi, biroq sovuq holda prokatka qilingan metall, yoki termik ishlov berilgandan keyin (masalan, toblashdan keyin) legirlangan metall payvandlangan bo'lsa, u holda bu hududda metallning boshlang'ich strukturasi tiklanadi. Bunda mustahkamlik biroz kamayadi, biroq metallning plastikligi ortadi.

500°C haroratdan past haroratgacha hudud (6) da strukturaning o'zgarishi yuz bermaydi. Biroq, metall bu yerda: metallni qo'shni hududlari isitib turgani sababli juda sekin soviydi va shuning uchun 100°C haroratgacha donlarning chegaralari bo'yicha aralashmalarning mikroskopik zarrachalari ajralishi mumkin. Bu hodisa metallning eskirishi deb ataladi. Eskirish natijasida qovushqoqlik kamayadi, bunga payvandlash vaqtida metallning issiqlikdan kengayishi oqibatida hosil bo'ladigan plastik deformatsiyalar ham yordam beradi. Qizitilganda ko'k tuslar hosil bo'ladigan harortgacha (200–400°C) qiziganida metallning mo'rtlashuvi ko'k tusda sinuvchanlik deb, hudud 6 esa mo'rtlik hududi deb ataladi. Termik ta'sir zonasining eni chok uzunligining birligaga to'g'ri keladigan issiqlik energiyasini miqdori – pogon energiyasiga bog'lik. Qo'lda yoy bilan payvandlashda, masalan, po'latni payvandlashda TTZ ning eni 5–6 mm ni tashkil etadi, gaz alangasida payvandlashda 25 mm gacha yetadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. Хатамова, З. (2021). Expenditure of income from taxes and levies in the kokand khanate: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1230>. In *research support center conferences* (No. 18.05).
2. Nazirjonovna, K. Z. (2022). SH. VOKHIDOV'S CONTRIBUTION TO THE STUDY OF THE HISTORY OF THE KOKAND KHANATE. *Innovative Society: Problems, Analysis and Development Prospects*, 139-141.
3. Хатамова, З. (2023). Из истории денежной политики в финансовой системе Коканского ханства. *Актуальные проблемы истории*

- Узбекистана, 1(1), 327–336. извлечено от <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/history-of-uzbekistan/article/view/16511>
4. Nazirjonovna, K. Z. (2022). Political-Financial Analysis of the Issues of Science of the Kokand Khanate in the Work of Khudoyorkhonzade “Anjum At-Tavorikh”. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY*, 3(10), 102-111. Retrieved from <https://cajssh.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJSSH/article/view/463>
 5. Burkhonov, I. M. (2020). “ZAKAT” HAS ENSURED FAIRNESS AND BALANCE IN SOCIETY. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 201-204.
 6. Muhiddinovich, B. I. (2020). Negative impact of the tax system on political life-on the example of the history of the Kokand Khanate (1850–1865). *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(5), 790-795.
 7. Burkhonov, I. (2021, June). The importance of the scientific heritage of asomiddin urinboyev in the study of the history of the Kokand khanat. In *Конференции*.
 8. Burkhonov, I. (2021). The importance of the scientific heritage of asomiddin urinboyev in the study of the history of the Kokand khanat: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1242>. In *RESEARCH SUPPORT CENTER CONFERENCES* (No. 18.05).
 9. Бурханов, И. (2023). Научное наследие Шарафиддина Али Язди в интерпретации Асомиддина Оринбоева. *Актуальные проблемы истории Узбекистана*, 1(1), 165–171.
 10. BURKHONOV, I. FROM THE HISTORY OF THE TRANSLATION OF THE WORK OF ABURAZZAK SAMARKAND" MATLA'I SA'DAYN AND MAJMA'I VAHRAIN. *ЭКОНОМИКА*, 138-144.

11. Muhiddinovich, B. I. (2022). The Importance of Asomiddin Urinboev's Scientific Research in the Study of the History of the Kokan Khanate. *Kresna Social Science and Humanities Research*, 3, 175-179.
12. Muhiddinovich, B. I. (2022). In the Study of the History of the Kokand Khanate. *Eurasian Journal of History, Geography and Economics*, 6, 68-71.
13. Burkhanov, I. . (2022). FROM THE HISTORY OF THE USE OF THE SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE OF KOKAND SCIENTISTS ASOMIDDIN URINBOEV. *International Bo'letín of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 2(10), 63–67.
14. Хатамова, З. (2021, August). EXPENDITURE OF INCOME FROM TAXES AND LEVIES IN THE KOKAND KHANATE: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1230>. In RESEARCH SUPPORT CENTER CONFERENCES (No. 18.05).
15. Хатамова, З. Н. Особенности налоговой системы Кокандского ханства / З. Н. Хатамова. — Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. — 2020. — № 5 (295). — С. 254-256. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/295/66918/>
16. Nazirjonovna, H. Z., & Abdumannobovich, N. M. (2020). Tax system on the territory of kyrgyzstan during the Kokand Khanate. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(6), 209-212.
17. Xatamova, Z. (2020). Expenditure of state funds replenished by taxes in the history of the kokand khanate. *EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD)*, 5(3), 274-277.
18. Nazirjonovna, K. Z. (2024). THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ZAKAT IN THE FINANCIAL SYSTEM OF THE KOKANDD KHAN. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 12(3), 100-105.
19. Nazirjonovna, K. Z. (2024). FROM THE HISTORY OF THE FINANCIAL SYSTEM OF THE KOKAND KHAN: CUSTOMS TAX AND OTHER

- COLLECTIONS. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 12(3), 94-99.
20. Nazirjonovna, K. Z. (2024). THE ISSUE OF CRAFTSMANSHIP IN THE FINANCIAL SYSTEM OF THE KOKAND KHANATE. *World Bo'letin of Public Health*, 31, 8-10.
21. Burkhanov I.A VIEW ON THE LIFE AND SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITY OF A. URINBOEV. (2024). *Synergy: Cross-Disciplinary Journal of Digital Investigation* (2995-4827), 2(11), 24-27. <https://multijournals.org/index.php/synergy/article/view/2639>
22. Burkhanov I. M. (2024). The Significance of A. Orinboev's Research in the Study of the Historical Heritage of the Turkish People. *Excellencia: International Multi-Disciplinary Journal of Education* (2994-9521), 2(11), 113-117. <https://doi.org/10.5281/>
23. Burkhanov I. M. (2024). The Significance of A. Urinboev's Research in the Study of the Historical Heritage of the Turkish People. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14095929>
24. Ilyosxon Muxiddinovich Burxonov Farg'ona, Markaziy Osiyo tibbiyot universiteti (CAMU) o'qituvchisi. (2024). XIV-XV ASR TARIXIGA OID MANBALARNI A.O'RINBOEV TADQIQOTLARIDA AKS ETISHI. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14061206>
25. Xatamova Zumradxon Nazirjonovna. (2023). QO'QON XONLIGI MOLIYAVIY TIZIMIGA ELCHILIK MASALALARINING TA'SIRI: XUDOYORXONZODANING "ANJUM AT-TAVORIX" ASARI ASOSIDA: THE IMPACT OF THE AMBASSADOR'S PROBLEMS ON THE FINANCIAL SYSTEM OF THE KOKAND-KHANATE: ON THE BASIS OF "ANJUM AT-TAVORIH" OF KHUDYAROKHANZODA. *Farg'ona Davlat Universiteti*, 28(5), 12. Retrieved from <https://journal.fdu.uz/index.php/sjfsu/article/view/2192>

26. Khatamova Zumradkhan Nazirjonovna. (2024). Important Islamic Sources in Studying the Financial System of the Kokan Khan. *Excellencia: International Multi-Disciplinary Journal of Education* (2994-9521), 2(11), 478-481. <https://doi.org/10.5281/>
27. Nazirjonovna, K. Z. (2024). The Issue of Financing Material-Architectural Culture in the History of the Kokan Khan. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY*, 4(11), 189–193. Retrieved from <https://inovatus.es/index.php/ejbsos/article/view/4603>
28. Khatamova Zumradkhan Nazirjonovna. (2024). An Organic Research of the History of the Turkish Nations: A Social Problem in the Financial System of the Kokand Khanate. *American Journal of Political Science and Leadership Studies*, 1(7), 30–32. Retrieved from <https://semantjournals.org/index.php/AJPSLS/article/view/505>
29. A VIEW ON THE LIFE AND SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITY OF A. URINBOEV. (2024). *Synergy: Cross-Disciplinary Journal of Digital Investigation* (2995-4827), 2(11), 24-27. <https://multijournals.org/index.php/synergy/article/view/2639>
30. The Significance of A. Urinboev's Research in the Study of the Historical Heritage of the Turkish People. (2024). *Innovative: International Multidisciplinary Journal of Applied Technology* (2995-486X), 2(11), 26-2 <https://multijournals.org/index.php/innovative/article/view/2633>

